

THE LACUNA AS A CULTURAL PHENOMENON IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: *Studies of lacunae in the language system, the text and the picture of the world is relevant direction of modern linguistics. The lacunarity phenomenon allows in a different way to look at the interpretational potential of the language system, evaluate ways compensation of missing forms, values, concepts in terms of identifying interpretive capabilities of multilingual systems. The article is devoted to the study of lacunae detected at different levels of comparable languages and cultures, and their influence on the course of intercultural communication. The relevance of the study is due to the need to further identify and study the national-cultural factors that influence the process of intercultural communication, in particular, translation activities.*

Keywords: *linguistic lacunae, translation model, culture, equivalent, lacuna, lacunology, motivate speech, connotative, semiotic sign, concept.*

Translation is a complex and multifaceted type of human activity. Although we usually talk about translating “from one language to another,” but in reality, in the process of translation, it is not just the replacement of one language by another. In translation, different cultures, different personalities, different thinking styles, different literatures, different eras, different levels of development, different traditions and attitudes clash. Cultural studies, ethnographers, psychologists, historians, literary critics are interested in translation, and various aspects of translation can be studied in the framework of the relevant sciences. The linguistic

model of the translation process represents it in the form of a series of successive transformations of the text of the original into the translation text, with the help of which the desired result can theoretically be achieved. The translation model is a conditional depiction of the translation process, based on an attempt to extend some general tenets of linguistics or psychology to the translation. Although any translation model is hypothetical, since there is no direct evidence that the translator acts exactly as it follows from this model, the coincidence of the translation result with the predicted one by the model shows that it has a certain explanatory power. In modern translation, there are several models of translation, which implies the ability to carry out the translation process in different ways. The most widespread are situational, transformational and semantic models.

Translation involves different approaches, that is, the same sentence can be translated, for example, with different stylistic coloring. The same word has many synonyms in the target language. This can be about infinity. So, translation is a complex, multifaceted concept that requires a specialist not only impeccable knowledge of the language, but also the ability to distinguish between semantic, stylistic, and so forth shades of written or oral speech; knowledge of the history of the language and knowledge of the history and development of the culture of society.

In translation studies lacuna are units that have a single-word nomination in another language. Lacunae are empty spaces in the system of language, vague concepts. Today, we believe that lacuna is a semiotic sign containing a zero plan of expression and a hidden or implicit plan of content. The modern linguistics, translation studies and nonverbal semiotics have birth to a new science that is becoming viral today – the lacunology, science with studies pauses in speech, cultural and linguistic gaps, lacunae of cognition, zero transfer. The expansion of many various methods and disciplines interfering resulted in the development of lacunology studies. Studies of lacunae in the language system, the text and the picture of the world is relevant direction of modern linguistics. The lacunarity

phenomenon allows in a different way to look at the interpretational potential of the language system, evaluate ways compensation of missing forms, values, concepts in terms of identifying interpretive capabilities of multilingual systems. The issue of lacunarity, scientists have been actively engaged for over 40 years. Scientists most often correlated lacunae in languages, cultures and knowledge in various pictures of the world with categories of ethnocultural orientation. The origins of lacunarity, the reasons of the formation and elimination of lacunae, have always attracted the attention of linguists.

Lacuna is a semantic value by which the type of equivalent relationship is determined. The semantic degree of equivalence and the semantic magnitude of the lacunae are inversely proportional to each other: the greater the semantic intensity of the lacuna, the smaller the semantic degree of equivalence, and vice versa. Equivalence and lacunae are associated with a change in the denotative structure of lexical meaning in the intercultural comparison of languages. Both concepts - lacuna and equivalence - are different sides of the same coin. In the denotative plan, units of lexical meaning that are not equivalent may in the context prove to be adequate

Lacunas, according to the scientists, are the differences that arise in each individual critical incident and have certain cultural discourses. This statement substantiates the introduction of the concept of an axiological lacuna, predetermining the difference in semantic meaning between cultures and languages.

The lacuna is always included in wider social and cultural contexts. Such an approach is required to analyze the lacunae in the context of perception and subsequent behavior of the recipient, in other words, the lacuna will be considered as a unit of perception. The logical continuation of the development of the theory of lacunae are the views of Sternin I.A., Bykova G.V., Eiger G., Panasyuk I., where they see the lacuna as a cognitive phenomenon. The authors proceed from a comparative analysis of the lacuna and the concept. From the position of Sternin

I.A., Bykova G.V., between the concept and the lacuna there are no deterministic relations. However, the researchers, defining the lacuna as a lexical gap in the presence of a concept, immediately note that concepts define the semantic character of the lacuna. In this there is a contradiction of this concept. However, Eiger G., Panasyuk I. adhere to a different point of view: “the lacuna is a signal of the absence of a concept and at the same time its lexical expression”.

Markovina I.Yu. makes an attempt to examine the ethno-psycholinguistic phenomenon of lacunae from the standpoint of culturology and social psychology, thereby revealing the psychological mechanisms underlying the phenomenon of cultural lacunary. I.Yu. Markovina developed a program for the elimination of lacunae, which correlates with the manifestation of the socio-psychological mechanisms of interethnic interaction and positions as a theory of understanding "foreign" culture.

Lacuna divided by different criteria, which will reflect linguistic and cultural reality. It is important to emphasize division of lacunae into linguistic and culturological. Linguacultural lacunae occupy an intermediate position. Lacunae defined by languages comparison are called linguistic: they are divergences, gaps, failures, emptiness in relation to the units of compared languages, in other words, interlinguistic or the units within one language (inside language lacunae). Discussing lacunae, I.V. Tomasheva mentioned “lacunae by languages comparison called linguistic, which in their turn, may be lexical, grammatical and stylistic, complete, partial or compensated”. Besides, linguistic lacunae may be unique and partial, motivated and unmotivated, speech, emotive, connotative, and zeroed. Lingucognitive approaches of Russian linguists to the study of lacuna typology were more fruitful. V.G. Gak’s pointed out that, interlinguistic lacunae are absence of words for a designation of concepts, which exist in the given society and which have the special verbal designation in the other language.

Lacunarity, as a phenomenon, is a property of the entire lexical system of a language. This phenomenon directly related to the systemic nature of the language,

which expressed and due to the non-verbality of our thinking, and the whole variety of thinking forms, a reflection of reality, as well as a fundamental difference in mental and language processes.

One of the important sections of the theory of lacunarity is the systematization of ways of filling lacunae, or their compensation: filling the lacunae is the process of disclosing the meaning of a certain concept (or word) belonging to a foreign culture. This filling can be of different depths, depending on the nature of the lacuna, on the type of text in which the lacuna exists, on the characteristics of the recipient. Lacuna compensation - the process of filling a lacuna reduced to the selection of an identical or quasi-identical element that will serve as an analogue of the "alien" image in its culture. This technique is used in cases where the lacuna cannot be preserved (as it is necessary to make the text as understandable as possible to a cultural reader), and it is impossible to fill it for one reason or another.

To date, there are various typologies of lacunae. I.A. Sternin and other scientists propose to isolate lacunae of several types:

- subject and abstract (according to the degree of abstractness of the content). Subject lacunae reflects the absence of a material, physical, sensually perceived object or phenomenon. Abstract lacunae reflects the absence of an abstract concept, a mental category.

- generic and specific (according to paradigmatic characteristics, place in the language paradigms). Generic lacunae reflects the absence of a common name for a class of objects, specific - the absence of specific names, names of individual types of objects or phenomena.

- motivated and unmotivated (for non-linguistic conditionality). Motivated lacunas are lacunas, which are explained by the absence of the corresponding object or phenomenon in the national culture. Unmotivated lacunae can not be explained by the absence of a phenomenon or object - there are corresponding objects and phenomena in culture, and there are no words for them.

- nominative and stylistic (by type of nomination). Nominative lacunae - lacunae, reflecting the absence of definite nomination. There may be no nomination of the subject in general, and there may be no emotional or evaluative nomination. Stylistic lacunae - the absence of a word with a certain stylistic characteristic, is a purely linguistic characteristic of the lacunae.

- part-lacunae gaps (for lacuna accessories to a certain part of speech). A verb may be in a language, but it may not have a single-root noun from it, etc.

Lacunae are national-specific elements of a culture, which are appropriately reflected in the language of the speakers of this culture, either not fully understood or misunderstood by carriers of a different culture and language in the process of communication. There are lacunae of various types: interlingual and intralingual, motivated and unmotivated, generic and specific, subject and abstract, nominative and stylistic.

Lacunae cause inconvenience in speech practice. It is not by chance that native speakers strive to get rid of the dismembered notation of reality, trying to express one-wordly any ideal content devoid of a lexical shell for the time being. This universal phenomenon is characteristic of all languages. It is the phenomenon of lacunarity that keeps our language "alive as life".

It should be noted that the types described indicate a lacuna as a linguocultural phenomenon that exists at different levels of language (speech) and culture. Lacunae, reflecting the specifics of a linguocultural society, are an obstacle to mutual understanding of the carriers of different cultures, therefore, the problem of lacunarity is particularly important in today's global world.

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